

THE THERMOPHYSICAL AND THERMAL SHOCK
RESISTANCE PROPERTIES OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The thermophysical properties of carbon-carbon composites, including the coefficient of thermal conductivity and the coefficient of thermal expansion were measured and examined from room temperature to 2000 C by means of laser flash technique, quartz differential dilatometry and laser scanning method. The thermal shock resistance properties of 3D fine woven carbon-carbon composite and 2D carbon cloth layup carbon-carbon composite were analyzed through the thermal shock resistance parameters. The effect of temperature, density as well as orientation on the thermophysical properties and thermal shock resistance property was investigated.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-carbon composites are new advanced materials and noted for their high specific strengths, high specific moduli, excellent ablation resistance and wear resistance properties. They are often utilized at very high temperatures as leading candidates for the heat protection materials on re-entry vehicles as well as in the nozzle system of rocket motors. Since many applications represent thermal stress situation, it is important to have a better understanding of their thermophysical and thermal shock resistance properties. There are numerous papers published regarding the mechanical properties of carbon-carbon composites (1-6). However, relatively little of them has been focused on their thermophysical and thermal shock resistance properties. It is the purpose of this study to

investigate the thermophysical and thermal shock resistance properties of carbon-carbon composites and correlate with their densities, orientations, temperatures as well as substrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two different types of carbon-carbon composites and six different kinds of samples were used in this study. They were:

1. CC-T1, a three dimensionally fine woven carbon-carbon composite with a density of about 1.95 g/cm^3 in Z orientation.
2. CC-T2, the same carbon-carbon composite as CC-T1 but in X-Y orientation.
3. CC-T3, the same carbon-carbon composite as CC-T1 but in 45 degree orientation.
4. CC-C1, a two dimensionally carbon cloth layup carbon-carbon composite with a density of about 1.40 g/cm^3 in the orientation parallel to the carbon cloths.
5. CC-C2, the same carbon-carbon composite in the same orientation as CC-C1 with a density of about 1.35 g/cm^3 .
6. CC-C3, the same carbon-carbon composite in the same orientation as CC-C1 with a density of about 1.30 g/cm^3 .

The processing details and mechanical properties of these carbon-carbon composites were reported previously [7-8].

The laser flash technique was used to determine and test the thermal diffusivities of carbon-carbon composites. A small sample about the size of a small coin is subjected to a very short burst of radiant energy from a laser. The resulting temperature rise of the rear surface of the sample is measured, and thermal diffusivity values are computed from the temperature rise vs. time data using equation:

$$\lambda = \frac{0.1388b^2}{t_{1/2}} \quad (1)$$

where λ is the coefficient of thermal diffusivity, b is the thickness of a sample, $t_{1/2}$ is the half time to maximum temperature rise [9]. The thermal conductivity values were calculated from the following equation:

$$K = \lambda CD \quad (2)$$

where K is the coefficient of thermal conductivity, λ is the coefficient of thermal diffusivity, C is the specific heat and D is the density. The coefficient of thermal expansion was determined by the quartz differential dilatometry from room temperature to 900°C, and from 1000°C to 2000°C by laser scanning method. The thermal shock resistance property of carbon-carbon composites was characterized by the thermal shock resistance parameter TSR, i.e.

$$TSR = \frac{\sigma K}{E \alpha} \quad (3)$$

where σ is the strength, K is the coefficient of thermal conductivity, E is the Young's modulus and α is the coefficient of thermal expansion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The coefficient of thermal conductivity values for the two different types of carbon-carbon composites in the different orientations from room temperature up to 2000 C were summerized in Figure 1. It is found with increasing temperature the coefficients of thermal conductivity decrease. For the two dimensionally carbon cloth layup carbon-carbon composites there are essentially linear relationships between the coefficients of thermal conductivity and the temperatures over the range of measurement. For the three dimensionally fine woven carbon-carbon composites the extent of change in coefficient of thermal conductivity with temperature is larger than that for the 2D carbon cloth layup carbon-carbon composites. The values of the coefficient of thermal conductivity are also closely related to the values of the density of the carbon-carbon composites. The higher the density the larger the coefficient of thermal conductivity. The density

Figure 1. The coefficients of thermal conductivity as a function of measurement temperature

of the CC-C1 is higher than that of the CC-C2, so the coefficient of thermal conductivity is also higher than that of the CC-C2 and the same case for the CC-C2 and CC-C3. The orientation of the carbon-carbon composites also strongly affect the values of the coefficient of thermal conductivity. The coefficients of thermal conductivity in different orientations at 200, 1000 and 2000°C are shown in Figure 2 for 3D fine woven carbon-carbon composite. It is obvious that the coefficients of

Figure 2. The coefficients of thermal conductivity in different orientations at 200, 1000 and 2000°C

thermal conductivity are greater in Z orientation than in X-Y orientations, and in X-Y orientations than in 45 degree orientation.

Changes in coefficient of thermal expansion with measurement temperature are shown in Figure 3. At all measurement temperatures up to 2000°C the coefficients of thermal expansion increase with temperature. The thermal expansion curves of both types of carbon-carbon composites were almost linear throughout the range of temperature tested. They are negative when the temperatures are below 600-700°C. At about 600-700°C the coefficients of thermal expansion are zero, and after that they become positive. The coefficients of thermal expansion of 3D fine woven carbon-carbon composites are greater than those of 2D carbon cloth layup carbon-carbon composites.

Figure 3. The coefficients of thermal expansion as a function of measurement temperature

The density and orientations of the carbon-carbon composites also play an important role in the values of the coefficient of thermal expansion. For the same type of carbon-carbon composite the higher the density the larger the coefficient of thermal expansion. The coefficients of thermal expansion of the 2D carbon cloth layup carbon-carbon composites

Figure 4. The coefficients of thermal expansion of CC-C type carbon-carbon composite at 200, 1000 and 2000°C

at 200, 1000 and 2000°C are shown in Figure 4. At 1000°C the coefficient of thermal expansion of CC-C3 ($D = 1.30 \text{ g/cm}^3$) is $+0.20 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, that of CC-C2 ($D = 1.35 \text{ g/cm}^3$) is $+0.25 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ and CC-C3 ($D = 1.40 \text{ g/cm}^3$) $+0.32 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$. For the CC-T type carbon-carbon composite the coefficients of thermal expansion in X-Y orientations are greater than those in Z orientation.

The results of the calculation of the thermal shock resistance parameter for both type of carbon-carbon composite at 1000 and 2000°C are listed in Table 1. It is evident that at 1000°C the values of the thermal

TABLE 1

The thermal shock resistance parameters of the carbon-carbon composites at 1000 and 2000°C

Materials	D (g/cm^3)	Orientation	TSR (Cal/ cm.s)	
			1000°C	2000°C
CC-C1	1.40	///	95	26
CC-C2	1.35	///	125	29
CC-C3	1.30	///	223	45
CC-T1	1.95	Z	1212	216
CC-T2	1.95	X-Y	942	214

shock resistance parameter are much greater than those at 2000°C. With increasing temperature the thermal shock resistance parameters decrease. The effect of the density and orientation on the thermal shock resistance parameter is relatively complex. It depends on the extends of change in σ , K , E , α . For different type of carbon-carbon composite they are different. No consistent trends were noted.

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